

**METHODOLOGY OF USING INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS
IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**

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Abstract in the article language in education interactive of the methods use and interactive of methods importance illuminated. Some interactive of methods application according to considerations held.

Key words: teaching methods, active educational, interactive education, education method, "Case study method, skill, qualification.

Modern education in the system technology, style and in tools significant changes happened is giving But one thing unchangeable - school of students knowledge level increase desire Students self to develop aspirations, self learning and that's it with own abilities improvements for knowledge level, teachers for main attention of learning the most important motive is cognitive activity formation and to develop focus important Study process organize in doing three main of the element sure compatibility work exit need:

- a) competencies in the form of expressed program goals and education results;
- b) educational the work forms and teaching methods;
- c) students of achievements evaluation tools and methods.

Education program done increase if its structure the following to questions sure answer to give possibility is successful _ will be:

- study of the program departments how competencies organize does ;

- how teaching methods certain competencies to develop possibility gives ;
- qualifications of formation check for how evaluation of means is used .

Education of the process success a lot in terms of applied teaching methods depend _ Teaching methods when you say teacher and of the student education goals to reach directed together activity methods is understood.

Education process of subjects pedagogical in process participation level according to you Interactive method study process of participants together work own into takes _ Interactive methods the most modern shape as to see possible the following methods share see :

Active method is a lesson in the process teacher and of the student mutually connection shape being, then students of the lesson active is a participant.

Interactive approach is mutual effect to do, conversation mode to be someone with communication to do Active of methods different like, interactive methods mutually to the effect directed.

Interactive method study process of participants together work own into takes Active teaching methods are special technique and of methods use with depends has been study process students in the process active study and cognitive to the activity attraction is to do Active education methods in practice is learning . That 's it from the system to use mean I think he is a teacher by ready knowledge present reach them _ remember storage and to multiply not but _ active mental and practical activity in the process knowledge and qualifications independent respectively to take over directed .

Current at the time education in the system the following active teaching methods wide used : problematic , interactive , game , research , modular , informational signals , critical situations , automated education and others _ Last times education theory and in practice wide of applied " education interactive methods " term " mutual the concept of " effect " . with is described . Definition of " Interactive " . traditional to methods alternative emphasizes . Interactive the process is pedagogical process of participants purposeful mutually effect and mutually effect process . Mutually relationships real vital to the experience based on , students between , students and teacher in the middle

thought exchange own into takes _ Interactive education is _ of students mutually influence , cooperation , cooperation based on built , training process together group in the activity done to be increased is education . Interactive methods to the students group in their work active to attend enable gives _ They are problematic issues discussion do , own point of view look right formation ability teaches . Problematic education methods systematic and purposeful apply independent knowledge efficiency significant level to increase help gives. That interactive of the methods one is Case-study is a method .

"Case-study" is an English word ("case" - specific situation, event, "study" - to learn, analyze) aimed at carrying out teaching based on the study and analysis of specific situations is a method. This method was first used in Harvard University in 1921 in order to use practical situations in the study of economic management sciences. In a case, open information or a specific event can be used as a situation for analysis. Case actions include: Who, When, Where, Why, How, What.

" Case- stage " implementation :

- There is problem or questions is placed
- Readers to the questions answers they write

Method statement : Web design. Creating a website using HTML and CSS

to the subject about questions is given Students this of questions each to one complete answer they give

Method assignment : HTML and CSS commands .

1	<head>...</head> tag in HTML ?
2	background in CSS parameter task?
3	<p>...</p> tag in HTML ?
4	hover parameter in CSS task ?
5	<div>...</div> tag in HTML task ?
6	The font-weight parameter in CSS task ?

Teacher answer :

1	<head>...</head> tag in HTML web the page right performance , styles , variety languages , har different on devices suitable respectively work provides _
2	background in CSS parameter in HTML appeal done tag for back background installation task performs _ Back background color or something to have a picture too can _
3	<p>...</p> tag in HTML separately text to write for is used . This is a tag into written to the text separate color, back background , styles our application can _
4	Hover parameter in CSS button or to the object mouse when it comes object color , shape , dimensions change , move can _
5	<div>...</div> tag in HTML very a lot used from tags one is considered This is a tag texts , forms , pictures and others separately to the blocks to separate them desired to the place to put , har one for separately styles to give service does _
6	The font-weight parameter in CSS appeal done of the text thickness level adjusts _ 300 too thin , 400 medium , 700 thick , 900 extreme thick _

The use of innovative methods to increase the efficiency of computer lessons, improving the skills of teachers depends primarily on their special professional potential. Taking into account the large number of hours of taught subjects, it is necessary to solve the problem of improving their knowledge in different ways. However, their methodological skills include such universal components that pedagogues of various educational subjects can use these components, and in this direction they can quickly achieve good results.

In conclusion, it should be said that as a result of the use of innovative technology, methods and methodologies in classes:

- students' desire to learn increases;

- thinking skills are developed;
- learns to think freely;
- his interest in the lesson increases;
- learns to listen to the opinion of others and respect them;
- learns to express his opinion freely and independently;
- teaches to work more on oneself;
- computer skills increase;
- the internet and skills to work with it will increase, etc

It can be seen that the application of the interactive method to the teaching process depends on the teacher's knowledge, skills, professional skills, and experience. In order to encourage students to be active in the lesson, the teacher should be able to choose questions and interactive methods that arouse interest in children. That's it lesson interesting to be with together intended to the result reach can _

REFERENCES USED:

1. Абрамова И. Г. Активные методы обучения в системе высшего образования. М. : Гардарики, 2008.
2. Бадаев А. А. Активные методы обучения. М., 2006.
3. Shaykhislamov, N. (2020). In the Field of Modern Linguistics – Linguoculturology. Мировая наука, 8(41), 33-36.
4. Shaykhislamov, N. (2020). Lingvokulturologiyaning tarixiy va nazariy asoslari. O‘zbekistonda ilm-fan va ta’lim, (2), 186-188.
5. Khonimkulov Ulugbek Suyunbaevich. The use of case-study technology in the formation of students' knowledge of computer hardware//JournalNX -A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal .2022 Y. 8 (03), 78–81 .
6. Tyutchenko, A.M. Innovatsionnaya pedagogicheskaya deyatelnost v vuzekak istochnikrazvitiya metodologii, teorii imetodiki obucheniya i vospitaniya / A.M. Tkachenko // Sovremennoe pedagogicheskoe obrazovanie. - 2021. -No4. -S. 96-99.